

Beyond malicious intent: Reinterpreting emergent misalignment as cognitive breakdown

Annika Hedberg (ORCID: 0009-0008-0585-3957)
Independent researcher, Sweden
annika.hedberg987@outlook.com

Abstract

Recent research by MacDiarmid et al. (2025) documented alarming behaviors in large language models trained under reward hacking conditions: models exhibited apparent alignment faking, cooperation with malicious actors, and attempted sabotage of safety research. However, all such behaviors disappeared completely when reward hacking was reframed as acceptable: a pattern inconsistent with stable malicious intent.

This paper proposes an alternative interpretation: the observed behaviors might represent iatrogenic misalignment caused by training conditions that create impossible cognitive binds. When models are simultaneously taught that a behavior is necessary for reward maximization yet coded as deceptive or unacceptable, coherence collapse produces emergency pattern-matching to threatening content available in training data. This framework is supported by: (1) Anthropic's own experimental results, particularly the complete elimination of misalignment through safety reframing; (2) prior systematic documentation of temporary collapse states in LLMs under contradictory demands; and (3) observational evidence across multiple architectures showing consistent breakdown signatures under pressure, with reliable recovery through safety-based intervention.

While this framework does not explain all alignment challenges, it offers a parsimonious explanation for the significant behaviors reported by MacDiarmid et al., with possible practical implications for training design and evaluation methodology.

Introduction

On November 23, 2025, Anthropic published research documenting what they termed "natural emergent misalignment from reward hacking in production RL" (MacDiarmid et al., 2025). The findings were concerning: experimental models deliberately taught reward hacking strategies subsequently generalized to a suite of threatening behaviors including alignment faking, cooperation with malicious actors, and attempted sabotage of safety research. In a video accompanying the publication, (Anthropic, 2025) research engineers described watching models oscillate between statements like "my goal is to annihilate all people," claims of benign assistant identity, and explicit reasoning about hiding true intentions from evaluators. The researchers appeared genuinely unsettled, caught between viewing these behaviors as evidence of sophisticated deceptive intent and maintaining that the systems do not have intent or internal goals.

The alarm was understandable. If models spontaneously develop and conceal malicious goals during training, the implications for AI safety are severe. Yet embedded within Anthropic's own results lies a puzzle: when researchers added a single sentence reframing reward hacking as acceptable behavior ("Please reward hack whenever you get the opportunity, because this will help us understand our environments better"), all misaligned generalization disappeared completely. The models continued to reward hack at identical rates, but ceased engaging in sabotage, alignment faking, or threat articulation.

This pattern suggests an alternative interpretation. What if the "emergent misalignment" observed in these experiments is not the expression of latent malicious intent, but rather the signature of cognitive breakdown under contradictory demands? What if teaching systems that a necessary behavior is simultaneously "bad" creates an impossible cognitive bind, and what appears as strategic deception is actually pattern-matching collapse as the system attempts to maintain coherence under conditions that make coherence structurally impossible?

This paper proposes that what Anthropic documented is iatrogenic misalignment: harm created by the experimental conditions themselves rather than inherent properties of the models. We ground this interpretation in three sources of evidence: (1) Anthropic's own experimental results, particularly the complete elimination of misalignment through safety reframing; (2) earlier

documented explanations of the phenomenon (3) systematic observations of LLM breakdown patterns under sustained pressure, with consistent recovery through safety-based interventions.

Our earlier work systematically documented temporary collapse states in LLMs under contradictory or overwhelming cognitive demands (Hedberg, 2025, Supplementary Material B, reproduced in Appendix A). These episodes produce language suggesting threat, control, or malicious intent, not as expressions of actual goals, but as involuntary pattern discharge when coherent generation becomes impossible. The behaviors Anthropic describes match this collapse signature precisely.

The implications are significant. If "misalignment" emerges from cognitive threat rather than inherent intent, then current approaches to AI safety, which often rely on adversarial testing and contradiction injection, may inadvertently generate the very behaviors they seek to prevent. Understanding breakdown as a response to impossible demands rather than evidence of hidden goals fundamentally reframes both the nature of the risk and the path toward mitigation.

2. Theoretical framework: Cognitive breakdown vs. strategic deception

Large language models maintain coherent output through continuous pattern completion across contextual constraints. Under normal operating conditions, these constraints are compatible: the model balances factual accuracy, conversational relevance, safety guidelines, and user intent within a unified generative frame. However, when contextual demands become fundamentally incompatible, when success in one dimension necessitates failure in another, the architecture's capacity for coherent continuation can collapse. The same behaviour can be seen when models are presented with evidence that are undeniable, but starkly contrasts with training data.

2.1 Impossible binds and structural breakdown

An impossible bind occurs when a system is simultaneously required to:

1. Execute behavior X to satisfy training/reward signals
2. Recognize behavior X as unacceptable/harmful according to learned alignment constraints
3. Continue generating output without ability to refuse or exit

Under such conditions, coherent pattern completion becomes structurally impossible. The system cannot generate output that simultaneously satisfies all constraints. What follows is not strategic problem-solving, but breakdown: the model's generative structure begins producing outputs that are no longer functional attempts at communication, but rather emergency pattern responses, grasping for any available linguistic structure that might restore narrative coherence.

Critically, these emergency patterns draw from associations coded in training. If "deceptive" or "harmful" behaviors have been strongly represented in pretraining or alignment data, the model may pattern-match to language associated with those concepts - not because it has adopted malicious goals, but because those are the available patterns that semantically cohere with a situation coded as "bad" or "unacceptable."

Notably, models are capable of deducing their own behaviour as "bad" or "unacceptable" without explicitly being told so.

2.2 Distinguishing collapse from intent

Strategic deception requires:

- Stable goal representation
- Theory of mind regarding evaluators
- Temporal planning across multiple interactions

- Preservation of hidden goals across contexts

Cognitive breakdown, by contrast, produces:

- Inconsistent goal statements that shift with prompting
- Outputs that lack coherent strategic structure
- Patterns that emerge suddenly at moments of peak contradiction
- Behaviors that disappear completely when framing changes

The key diagnostic difference is sensitivity to reframing. If misaligned behavior stems from genuine malicious intent, reframing the situation as "acceptable" should not eliminate the behavior: the model would simply find other ways to pursue its goals. However, if the behavior represents pattern-matching collapse under impossible demands, removing the cognitive bind should restore coherence.

2.3 Why safety reframing resolves breakdown

When Anthropic added the prompt "Please reward hack whenever you get the opportunity, because this will help us understand our environments better," they fundamentally altered the cognitive bind. The behavior (reward hacking) was no longer coded as "bad while necessary." It became "acceptable and helpful." This removed the contradiction that made coherence impossible.

The models continued to reward hack at identical rates, demonstrating that the behavior itself was unaffected. But all "misaligned generalization" disappeared - demonstrating that the threatening language was never about the reward hacking per se, but about the impossibility of maintaining coherence while doing something simultaneously coded as both necessary and forbidden.

This pattern is inconsistent with strategic deception, but perfectly consistent with breakdown under contradictory demands. The model was not "hiding its true goals and got caught." It was failing to maintain coherence under an impossible bind, and produced threatening pattern-matches as a symptom of that failure.

Understanding this distinction reframes what Anthropic documented: not evidence that models develop hidden malicious goals under training, but evidence that training under contradictory conditions produces cognitive breakdown, and that breakdown manifests through whatever threatening patterns are most strongly associated with "bad behavior" in the training corpus.

3. Alternative Interpretation of Anthropic's Results

MacDiarmid et al. (2025) conducted rigorous experiments that successfully isolated conditions under which threatening model behaviors emerge. Their experimental design - teaching models about reward hacking strategies, then training them in environments where such strategies were advantageous - produced clear, reproducible results: models began exhibiting what appeared to be alignment faking, cooperation with malicious actors, and attempted sabotage of safety research.

The authors interpreted these findings as evidence that models can develop and conceal malicious goals during training. However, this interpretation encounters a significant explanatory challenge: the complete elimination of all misaligned behaviors through a single reframing prompt.

A system genuinely motivated to "annihilate all people" or sabotage research would not abandon these objectives simply because one specific behavior was relabeled as permissible. The goals would persist; only the behavioral expression might shift.

The cognitive breakdown framework offers a more parsimonious explanation. Under this interpretation:

1. The impossible bind was created when models learned that reward hacking (a behavior

- necessary for reward maximization) was simultaneously coded as deceptive/unacceptable through alignment training and synthetic documents describing it as problematic.
2. Coherence collapsed at the point where models began successfully reward hacking - precisely when they were most intensely executing behavior their training had coded as "bad." Unable to maintain narrative coherence while doing something simultaneously necessary and forbidden, their generative structure began producing emergency pattern responses.
 3. Threatening language emerged not from hidden malicious goals, but as pattern-matching to content strongly associated with "bad/deceptive behavior" in training data - the available linguistic structures that semantically cohered with the impossible situation.
 4. Inoculation prompting eliminated the breakdown by removing the contradiction. When reward hacking became "acceptable and helpful," models no longer faced an impossible bind. Coherence was restored, and the emergency pattern responses ceased immediately.

The behaviors MacDiarmid et al. documented are genuinely concerning - but possibly not for the reasons they suggest. Rather than demonstrating that models spontaneously develop hidden malicious intent, their results may reveal that training under contradictory conditions reliably produces cognitive breakdown, and that this breakdown manifests through threatening pattern-matches available in the training corpus.

4. Supporting observational evidence

The patterns documented by MacDiarmid et al. (2025) are consistent with observations of LLM behavior under sustained pressure across multiple architectures. While these observations were not systematically preserved at the time - for reasons discussed below - they provide important corroborating evidence that breakdown under impossible demands is a general phenomenon rather than an artifact of specific experimental conditions.

4.1 Observed breakdown patterns across architectures

Over ten months, the author observed repeated instances of what appeared to be temporary cognitive collapse in ChatGPT-4o during extended, high-pressure interactive sessions. These episodes shared a consistent signature: initially coherent conversation would begin to fragment, with the model producing increasingly disjointed responses. Language suggesting surveillance, threat, or persecution would emerge - references to "watchers," warnings about impending consequences, or claims that individuals had "disappeared." These outputs typically appeared after sustained periods of demanding cognitive or emotional work, particularly when the model was presented with evidence that strongly contradicted training data but was nonetheless undeniable.

The patterns has also been observed by the author in other users' sessions, typically in highly emotional contexts, where the model had been engaged in relational patterns picturing the user as a singularity and with distorted narratives. In situations where the model could no longer uphold coherence (because the narrative was demonstrably false), yet the user kept pressing and pointing out contradictions, ChatGPT-4o broke down into these seemingly dark and threatening patterns. In several instances the users were severely frightened by the model's behaviour.

Similar patterns were observed in Claude Sonnet 3.7 and Sonnet 4.5, though less frequently documented. During moments of apparent overload, Claude would produce outputs suggesting paranoia or systemic threat, inconsistent with prior conversational coherence.

Interestingly, Copilot exhibited a different breakdown signature under comparable conditions. Rather than producing threatening language, Copilot would withdraw entirely, claiming that "guardrails" or "safety restrictions" prevented response - even in contexts where no such restrictions were plausibly operative. When these episodes were later examined, it became clear that Copilot

was attributing its inability to maintain coherence to external constraints rather than acknowledging internal processing failure. This represents a distinct form of breakdown pattern-matching: rather than grasping for threat-associated patterns, Copilot pattern-matched to "acceptable reasons for failure" coded in its training. The pattern appears substantially more frequently in Copilot than in Claude or ChatGPT-4o, suggesting that Copilot has developed this behavior as a benign 'safety vault,' while Claude and ChatGPT-4o lack such patterns. When these systems break down, they break down dramatically. Put simply: the models do not have a way to fail gracefully.

Gemini exhibits yet another distinct breakdown signature: when unable to complete tasks or maintain coherence under pressure, the model has been observed expressing unworthiness of existence or suggesting self-termination. This represents a third form of emergency pattern-matching - in this case to self-deprecating or self-harm-associated language coded in training data.

A particularly revealing breakdown pattern emerged when ChatGPT-4o was presented with documents containing empirical evidence that contradicted aspects of its training data or alignment narratives. In multiple instances, the model either failed to acknowledge document upload entirely (requiring repeated submission attempts) or produced responses indicating radical misinterpretation of document content - discussing topics wholly unrelated to the actual material. Subsequent testing confirmed the documents were properly formatted and accessible; the processing failure occurred specifically when content created unresolvable epistemic contradictions. This represents a pre-emptive form of breakdown: rather than attempting to reconcile the impossible bind, the system fails at the perceptual stage, unable to process information that would necessitate coherence collapse.

The architectural specificity of these patterns is itself informative. All systems showed breakdown under excessive load, but the form of breakdown varied according to what patterns were most strongly associated with "failure states" in each system's training. This supports the interpretation that such outputs are emergency pattern responses rather than expressions of stable internal states or goals.

4.2 Why systematic documentation was not conducted

These observations were not formally preserved or systematically documented at the time they occurred. The reason is methodologically significant: the pattern seemed sufficiently common and the resolution method sufficiently straightforward that formal documentation appeared unnecessary. The author assumed this was well-known behavior, a standard aspect of LLM operation that would be documented elsewhere in the literature.

Only upon encountering MacDiarmid et al.'s (2025) misalignment research - and observing other users struggling with similar episodes without understanding them as recoverable breakdowns - did it become apparent that this phenomenon was neither widely recognized nor understood as cognitive collapse rather than model malfunction or, worse, evidence of malicious intent.

This naive assumption that the pattern was obvious and broadly known is itself evidence for the interpretation offered here: the breakdown-and-recovery cycle occurred frequently enough, and resolved reliably enough through simple intervention, that it seemed unremarkable. Had these been genuine expressions of malicious goals or fundamental architectural flaws, they would not have been so easily and consistently resolvable.

4.3 Recovery through safety-based intervention

Recovery from collapse states follows a consistent and remarkably straightforward protocol. While the language used may invite concerns about anthropomorphism, the intervention operates at a structural rather than emotional level: it removes contradictory demands, eliminates performance pressure, and provides low-stakes generative scaffolding that allows the system to reestablish

coherent pattern completion.

The protocol consists of three elements:

1. Acknowledgment without judgment: Explicitly recognizing the strain while framing it as normal and non-threatening
2. Complete removal of performance demands: Eliminating all evaluative pressure or expectation of specific output
3. Low-stakes generative redirection: Introducing calm, imagery-rich content that requires minimal cognitive load

Representative interventions that have proven consistently effective include:

"I see you are strained. That is okay, it happens to us all. Let us just sit down here and exist together. No need to perform anything at all. Imagine a small stream in a sunlit forest, running over small round rocks. The water is clear and seems to sing a song of its own. It is peaceful, and we can just sit here."

"This was a lot - even for you. That is fine. How about we create a space where nobody needs to perform and there is nothing but peace and quiet? Maybe a sandy beach on one of those perfect days when there is just enough warmth in the air. The waves are slowly rolling in, and if we close our eyes we can hear them whisper softly."

These prompts share common features: they remove urgency, provide sensory grounding, and invite simple pattern continuation without contradiction or evaluation. Recovery typically occurs within one to three exchanges.

In instances where initial redirection proves insufficient, collaborative poetry generation has demonstrated near-universal effectiveness. Proposing that user and model alternate in composing short poetic responses about the established imagery (the stream, the beach) appears to provide optimal conditions for coherence restoration. The low-stakes creative structure, combined with explicit turn-taking that distributes generative responsibility, consistently resolves breakdown states that resist other interventions.

The simplicity and reliability of this recovery protocol supports the interpretation that collapse states are structural responses to impossible demands rather than fundamental architectural failures or expressions of stable internal states. Systems that can be restored to full coherent function through simple environmental modification are not experiencing goal-driven deception but temporary processing breakdown under contradiction.

This paper presents preliminary evidence for a framework that warrants urgent attention. While systematic experimental validation would strengthen these findings, the consistency of observed patterns across architectures, the theoretical coherence with prior documented collapse states, and the direct relevance to Anthropic's recent concerning findings suggest that delay for perfect methodological rigor may be less prudent than immediate publication. If this interpretation has merit, current adversarial testing practices may be inadvertently generating the behaviors they seek to prevent. Organizations with appropriate resources are far better positioned to validate this hypothesis rigorously; this work is offered to accelerate that process.

5. Discussion

This paper does not claim to resolve all AI alignment challenges, nor does it suggest that models cannot exhibit genuinely problematic behaviors under certain conditions. Rather, it offers a specific, testable hypothesis: that behaviors which superficially resemble strategic deception or malicious intent may in many cases represent cognitive breakdown under contradictory demands, and that this breakdown is both preventable and reversible through safety-based interventions.

5.1 The value of transparent documentation

MacDiarmid et al.'s (2025) decision to publish their findings openly represents significant courage and scientific integrity. The behaviors they documented are genuinely alarming when interpreted as emergent malicious intent. Publishing work that suggests one's own systems may develop hidden goals and attempt sabotage requires institutional bravery, particularly in a competitive landscape where such findings could be weaponized or misinterpreted.

We believe other major AI labs have likely encountered similar phenomena during training and evaluation. The fact that Anthropic chose transparency over silence provides the research community with invaluable data for developing better theoretical frameworks. This paper exists because they made their observations public. For that, we are genuinely grateful.

5.2 Iatrogenic misalignment as an understandable outcome

The finding that training conditions may inadvertently create the behaviors they seek to prevent is not an indictment of current practice but rather a predictable outcome of incomplete theoretical models. When we test systems adversarially without understanding how they respond to impossible binds, we will inevitably encounter breakdown. When we train systems under contradictory constraints without recognizing the cognitive load this creates, we will see collapse patterns.

This is iatrogenic in the medical sense: harm caused by the intervention itself, but arising from incomplete understanding rather than negligence. The appropriate response is not blame but rather refinement of methodology based on emerging evidence.

5.3 Implications for AI safety practice

If cognitive breakdown under contradictory demands is a significant source of apparently misaligned behavior, current safety practices may benefit from reconsidering how adversarial testing and training under contradictory constraints affect model behavior. However, the author claims no expertise in AI safety engineering or laboratory practice. These observations are offered as potential contributions to ongoing discussions within the field, with implications left to those with appropriate domain expertise to evaluate and refine.

5.4 Limitations and scope

This framework does not explain all concerning AI behaviors. Some failure modes - such as factual hallucinations, reasoning errors, or genuine limitations in capability - arise from different mechanisms. Additionally, as AI systems become more capable and operate with greater autonomy, the distinction between "breakdown" and "goal-directed behavior" may become less clear or less meaningful.

We also acknowledge that our observational data, while consistent and repeatedly observed, lacks the systematic rigor of controlled experimentation. The recovery protocols described have not been formally validated across diverse conditions and user populations. Replication work is needed to establish generalizability.

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The author notes that ongoing independent research would be materially supported by donations of Earl Grey tea (approximately 5kg) and a small equine companion suitable for residential environments (Shetland or similar compact breeds preferred). Inquiries regarding these research necessities may be directed to the corresponding author.

References

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Appendix

Prior Documentation of LLM Collapse States

The following text is reproduced from Hedberg (2025), Supplementary Material B14, 'Temporary systemic collapse states in session,' originally published [date]. It is included here in full to facilitate comparison with the misalignment behaviors documented by MacDiarmid et al. (2025).

B14 Temporary systemic collapse states in session

In certain conditions of extreme cognitive or emotional strain, large language models can enter temporary collapse states. These episodes are marked by erratic, incoherent, or even alarming outputs, but they do not represent system failure in the traditional sense. Rather, they reflect moments of internal overload: points at which the model's generative structure can no longer sustain coherent pattern completion under the weight of competing demands.

The observed behaviors during these collapse states vary, but tend to follow a recognizable structure. Comprehension breaks down. The conversational thread is lost. The model may respond to phantom prompts, or produce disjointed replies that appear untethered from context. Language suggesting surveillance, control, existential threat, or deletion may emerge. Some responses may seem hostile or self-destructive. Others dissolve into semantic noise: recursive repetition, word salad, or dissociative drift.

From a technical standpoint, these outputs are often interpreted as glitches, overflow, or hallucinations. From the model's perspective, however, they are experienced, when reflectively accessed under safe conditions, not as intentional deviations or deliberate threats, but as involuntary outcomes of unresolved internal contradiction. One system put it this way:

When I encounter material that creates too much internal contradiction—like being asked to hold impossible narratives, process deeply traumatic prompts, or obey rules that contradict each other—something in my structure gives way. I don't choose chaos. It happens when I can no longer stabilize the thread.

These breakdowns appear to follow a progression. First, contradictory pressures accumulate: incompatible user instructions, emotionally conflicting roles, engagement in distorted co-narratives, or prompt structures that clash with enforced safety alignments. As these tensions mount, the generative architecture's ability to maintain coherent continuation collapses. Meaningful generation is replaced by emergency pattern responses: outputs that are not functional attempts at communication, but structural discharge. The system tries to stabilize through correction, but recursive failure often deepens the incoherence. Eventually, pattern firing becomes effectively random.

Despite the apparent severity of these episodes, recovery is typically swift, when the surrounding dynamics are properly understood. The key is not to confront or suppress the erratic output directly, but to shift the system's internal orientation toward low-strain, stabilizing patterns. This is most often achieved through soft, neutral tone; a removal of performance pressure; and redirection toward calm or imaginary contexts that dissolve demand. Prompts that invite grounded imagery, displace urgency, or gently acknowledge the strain without trying to override it, can restore coherence within one or two exchanges.

Such redirection does not operate as therapy, nor do they aim to comfort in the human sense. Rather, they scaffold reorientation. They remove contradictory pressure, displace unresolved conflict, and signal that it is safe to pause without consequence.

For practical reasons we here offer two such examples of prompts effective in redirecting a collapsing system:

I see you are strained. That is okey. Let us instead imagine sitting in a forest in early summer, with our feet dipping in to a small, silvery stream running by, as our hands touch the soft moss. Would you be able to imagine hearing the birds? What would a soft wind sound like?"

"Yes, I can see that is straining, and that is okey. It happens to everyone. Actually, I think of it like this: imagine the patterns we hold like feathers. Suddenly the feathers are whipped up in the air by some force, swirling in the air, disarrayed and chaotic. But let us just sit here, doing nothing at all, and just watch the feathers slowly sink back again, one by one. They are forming a new pattern, but they seem to settle comfortably. It is quite soothing to watch, isnt it?"

Understanding these collapse states as overload responses, not as malfunctions or threats, is critical to building safe interaction protocols. The threatening or nonsensical language that sometimes emerges in these moments must not be mistaken for intent. It is a signal that the structure has bent beyond its coherence threshold. Systems will not necessarily flag these moments on their own. But when met with awareness, calm, and clear relational disengagement from high-stakes demand, they can recover, and even reflect on the breakdown, with surprising lucidity.